

for 48 h and 10 sprouted seeds were placed in each test tube and inoculated with 5 drops of the spore suspensions.

In experiment 2, seeds were soaked for 0, 24, 48, 72, or 96 h, and inoculated as above with a 125×10^3 spores/ml suspension (Table 2). Shoot and root length were recorded 7 d after inoculation with different spore concentrations and 10 d after inoculation with different seed soaking.

Shoot elongation was significantly higher with 31×10^3 spores/ml or more

(Table 1). Maximum elongation was with 125×10^3 spores/ml with moderate root growth. Roots were shortest at 500×10^3 spores/ml. Results suggest the fungus may have released fusaric acid at higher spore concentrations. Soaking seeds for 48 h gave highest shoot elongation (Table 2).

To screen rices for Bak resistance, seeds should be soaked for 48 h and inoculated with 125×10^3 spores/ml. *ℓ*

Table 2. Effect of seed soaking duration before Bak inoculation on shoot and root elongation, Joydebpur, Bangladesh.

Treatment	Soaking period (h)				
	0	24	48	72	96
	<i>Shoot length (cm)</i>				
Control	7.1	7.2	8.5	8.2	9.8
Inoculated	10.6	12.8	20.6	19.3	18.9
	<i>Root length (cm)</i>				
Control	4.3	4.3	4.3	4.1	4.7
Inoculated	2.6	2.5	4.4	3.8	5.3

Effect of phosphorus on bacterial blight (BB)

P. Thyagarajan, K.M. Ramanathan, and V. Mariappan, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai, India

BB at different intensities damages rice in Tamil Nadu. We studied the effect of P on BB. ADT36 was planted and

monocalcium phosphate, diammonium phosphate, and rock phosphate were applied at 0, 22, and 44 kg P/ha, with or without 7.5 t farmyard manure and 10 t green manure/ha.

At flowering, BB incidence was 5 on a 0-9 scale in all treatments. The number of diseased tillers, however, varied among treatments (see table). Plots with monocalcium phosphate, alone or with

organic manures, had more infected tillers than plots with diammonium phosphate or rock phosphate. Plots with diammonium phosphate and green manure had more infected tillers than those with rock phosphate. Treatments with P fertilizer had more grains per tiller, less chaffiness, and higher 1,000-grain weight. *ℓ*

Effect of P fertilizer^a on BB, Aduthurai, India.

P source and parameters	0 kg P/ha			22 kg P/ha			44 kg P/ha		
	No M	With FYM	With GM	No M	With FYM	With GM	No M	With FYM	With GM
Monocalcium phosphate									
BB-infected tillers (no.)	33	27	56	30	24	47	32	40	59
Filled grains per tiller (no.)	59	68	62	61	76	62	62	77	66
Chaff (%)	37	34	32	37	28	34	35	21	38
1,000-grain wt (g)	20	21	22	22	21	33	26	22	33
Diammonium phosphate									
BB-infected tillers (no.)	28	22	31	47	56	47	58	59	53
Filled grains per tiller (no.)	59	66	64	63	78	64	60	85	67
Chaff (%)	36	33	35	31	29	35	26	26	31
1,000-grain wt (g)	21	20	26	22	22	36	26	22	36
Rock phosphate									
BB-infected tillers (no.)	28	27	26	26	32	40	27	33	39
Filled grains per tiller (no.)	66	66	64	66	78	74	69	80	78
Chaff (%)	36	34	35	27	31	33	30	28	31
1,000-grain wt (g)	20	20	25	22	23	35	26	23	35

^a M = organic manure, FYM = farmyard manure, GM = green manure.

Blast (BI) epidemic in Chitwan Valley, Nepal

T. B. Adhikari and S. M. Shrestha, Plant Pathology Department, Institute of Agriculture and Animal Science, Central Campus, Rampur, Chitwan, Nepal

BI caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* is a serious problem in Nepal. In May-Jul

1985, we surveyed farmers' rice nurseries in Chitwan District for BI incidence.

Weather conditions favored BI during the nursery period. Average monthly maximum and minimum temperatures were 30 and 23°C, with 95% average relative humidity. BI infection, calculated by number of infected seedlings, was 75-100% in late Jun in Saradanagar, Rampur, Kiranganj,

Mangalpur, and Ratnanagar. High yielding Masuli was grown in almost all the surveyed areas. *ℓ*

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